

PILE OF FOUNDATIONS TYPES AND APPLICATION METHODS STUDY

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Abstract: In empty lands facility set up reach for from long ago piled up from foundations using bride That's the main thing The reason is , first of all , the stake stumble in the process his surroundings and under of grunts to densification if it is reached , secondly , from above of the descending load pile whole body across to the gruntis transmitted . That's why also pegged for foundations in practice to apply last in years more developed went

Key words : pile , foundation , length , soil , construction , technique .

With a stake foundations to the task according to one how many to species is divided . In the depths of the soil work to the conditions monad respectively suspension piles and superior piles there is . Columnpiles all empty sh layers cut past , ends with strong to the grunt is installed .

If the rock to the grunts arrived to go opportunity if so , to them installation the most to the goal is appropriate . In this facility the ground real in a sense strong to sink almost face does not give

Column of piles facility device as work essence simple of the columns less different , pile grunt between them the work in the process almost does not participate .

Hanging piles ends strong to grunts arrived doesn't go Of piles this type solid ground layer deep is located cases is used . [1]

Such piles between is located grunts piles with together Such stakes between is located grunts piles with together works It is empty to the grunt tripped , or installed pile the surface among the grunt along resistance strength to the body will come .

Piles to the soil freeze from the depth significant level lower to the depth is immersed , this on the ground non-freezing soil lateral friction of the layer forces swollen to go from the layer friction from strength increases .

Cross it section according to piles round , square , straight rectangle , polygon and another in forms , longitudinal section according to cylinder , prism , cone and bottom part extended in appearances is prepared . Piles in the installation stuttering , water using shaking , pressure under compression and twist input methods is used . Preparation according to the piles assembly (steel pipes , assembly reinforced concrete piles), cast (mainly concrete is used) and mixed to species is divided .

Above brought foundations types piled up foundations enters With a stake foundations empty in grunts facility set up in reaching from long ago piled up from foundations using bride That's the main thing The reason is , first of all , the stake stuttering his surroundings and under of grunt to densification if it is reached , secondly , from above of the descending load pile whole the surface across to the grunt is transmitted . That's why also pegged for foundation in practice apply last in years more developed went With a stake foundations to the task according to one how many to species is divided .

In Grunt work to the conditions suitable respectively suspension piles and superior piles is available .

With a stake foundations : a) pillar pile ; b) suspension pile ; Column piles all empty grunts layer cut past , ends with strong to the grunt is installed . If the rock to the grunts arrived to go opportunity if so , to them installation the most to the goal according to In this facility the ground real in a sense strong to sink

almost face does not give

Column of piles facility device as work essence simple of the columns less different , pile grunt between them the work in the process almost does not participate .[2]

Hanging piles ends strong to grunts arrived doesn't go of the foundation such types solid ground layer deep is located cases is used . Such piles between is located grunts piles with together works It's empty to the grunt tripped or installed pile the surface among the grunt along resistance strength to the body will come .

With a stake of foundations economic efficiency and reliability increase the most important from directions one them count and design methods improvement .

With a stake of foundations different aspects learned local and foreign of scientists achievements designers and to the builders construction the time shorten and funds saving necessity account received without the most difficult in the circumstances constructions design and to build complicated problems successful solution to do enable gave

Pile of foundations deformations observation results construction constructions and pile foundations count and design methods improvement as well them to stop according to own on time measures to see for their work learning for is used .

Construction during pile foundations of the foundation deformations observation construction organization by or with him Created contract according to specialized organization by done is increased .

This observations results building or the facility manager of the organization acceptance to do document with present done project documents the introduction a must

Usage during piled up foundations of the foundation deformations observation the need for building and pile foundation design authors by solution

will be done and customer with agreed .

Construction and exploitation during pile foundations of the foundation deformations observation according to affairs this observations done which increases organizations by Created and building and pile foundation project authors as well customer with agreed upon special programs according to done is increased .

Observations special Created characters and indicators according to will be held , them placing in the program defined whole observation period during their safety provide based on done increase need

The program in making foundation of the foundation deformations observation according to current to recommendations action to do need .[3]

New scientific developments and calculation methods current to do contribution added , pile to build modern technologies to the road put them in practice check provided , stake direction to develop contribution added designers and of builders contribution separately note reached it won't be . modern foundation in engineering .

From piles of use economic efficiency Advances in science , new technologies and of construction technical base create their optimal design the solution search with one in line important important have So making a pile of the foundation one different load bearing ability different roads with to be provided possible : piles of the section size increase , but their the length reduce the length don't change it , but piles section increasing their the number reduce foundation and others , that is , the optimal solution choose opportunity almost each always exists , but this each is always clear not this not only of piles mutually effect account received without him search algorithm work exit the issue raised .

Sandy in grunts friction , in clays while connection power , mainly , the ground strength determines Low and high with grill piled up foundations . Oar shaped piles . Head arrows direction according to piled up foundations oddly and

paddle shaped to species is divided .

Simple piles axis is vertical steel , that of paddlefis while effect carrying load in the N direction relatively a corner organize is enough Such devices prop walls , vaulted structures , coast stagnation provider structures foundations to the ground is installed .

With a stake foundations set up in reaching the following from items used : wood , concrete , reinforced concrete and iron. They cross section according to : round , longer , square , straight rectangle and polygon in the form of longitudinally section according to and : cylinder , conical , bottom part extended without to be made can

With a stake foundations stuttering , water using shaking , pressure under squeeze and twist methods using is installed . Preparation condition also pegged on foundations don't collect and whole will be Do not collect piles in the enterprise made , construction to the field ready without is brought , whole piles while that's it you're welcome in itself project based on is prepared .

Overall of the stake 4.5-15 m long , connected ones and up to 20-25 m to be can With that together their transversely the cross section is less than 18-20 cm not to be need Wood from piles use the following advantages has :

- during installation complicated does not require armor and strong that it was for to transport comfortable installation on time extension opportunity there is

- full soaked in grunts or water under flawless and continuous works

Concrete piles construction in the field in the project defined in levels casting without is prepared .

for this known at the points stumbling , pressing input or drilling from the equipment one using pits is dug . And that 's it pits concrete with filled and filled . Pipe into concrete from sending before in it the water suck get need Pipe watering get in the process in it concrete the pit by filling goes How much is the grunt in this empty if so , concrete beds that's all wider place occupies Pipe suction in the

process his because in the void everyone time concrete to be importance to give need Otherwise , the grunt will fall into the gap mold and concreting quality and pile load ability reduction can A. E. Strauss pile : a) to teach process ; b) ready pile ; 1st pipe; 2nd time; 3-concrete Concrete piles advantage that is , them in preparation of grunt balance status preserved , nearby to buildings dynamic effect is that it does not . With that together them installation on time quality observation opportunity limited sometimes of concrete hardening in the process sisot waters harmful effect is enough [4]

Reinforced concrete piles last in years foundation as wide is being used . That's the main thing the reason is theirs enterprise conditions made and ready without is used . With that together reinforced concrete from piles sisot waters from the level strictly look use can

Reinforced concrete piles cross the fraction according to square , polygon and round in the form is prepared . them 200-300 varieties in preparation of concrete is used . Longitudinal fittings the work performs , transversal while they are balance to keep service does Reinforced concrete piles whole and pore in case to be made can

Overall of piles die size It is 400x400 mm , 4 pieces with 100 mm reinforcement longitudinally and from a transverse iron ring consists of Transverse in practice the section is 200x200 mm piles are also available . Reinforced concrete piles length in the range of 5-20 m will be

Reinforced concrete piles : a) whole ; b) cavity . Iron stakes as basically pipe is used . They are reinforced concrete piles such as hit , water using oscillating or twist input methods using is installed .

Screw installable of piles bottom in the part special particles will be The stake installation in the process into come in take the rest of the grunt thrown away place concrete with is filled .

Various kind of and of structures from foundations use efficiency only their

design options and design of solutions technical and economic basics based on determination can

In justification of construction given engineering-geological conditions use for technical requirements answer giving all kind of foundations account get need

Pile foundation options technical and economic justification the following own into takes :

Seeing outgoing kind of foundation or seeing outgoing in the circumstances different different in design from piles of use technical to the goal compliance and rationality analysis to do ; [6]

Constructive solutions their constructiveness and exploitative reliability point of view in terms of analysis to do

Project solutions technical and economic indicators comparative analysis to do

Compared options for cost indicators are a single estimate and regulatory and legal from the base or indicators to determine common principles used without structures and materials single price for level one different construction of the area conditions for be counted need. Seeing outgoing foundation or pile types known in the soil and construction of the platform another conditions of use technical in terms of acceptability (guaranteed the work quality with foundation work release provide , this in size foundation elements construction platform inside and outside transport opportunity given soil conditions piles necessary level driving opportunity and others

Real opportunitywork done which increases construction of the organization technical equipment account received without selected kind of foundation and pile constructions installation according to things perform

Foundation of putting acceptability and given soil conditions project required by lifting piles ability get opportunity

Various kind of foundations compared to , only reasonable structures

account get need That 's it means :

For example , linear and piled up foundations in comparison initially each one in the round all possible has been of options of the basis reasonable type determination and after them each other with to compare need

of the foundation thorough work developed version foundation the design is not optimal certain object with an option for to compare possible it's not ;

Seeing outgoing options the number reduce for from unity significant level difference who does of piles raise ability to a low utilization rate have options seeing from exit out to throw or this coefficient to increase aspire to them again work need (coefficient according to) . of piles raise ability use , building or from the facility removable common project load his in the foundation all of piles bearing capacity with permission done common to the load ratio .

That's right assessment for compared foundations one different the work conditions provide for intended to be need , one different count reliability level and above ground part and soil conditions one different planning solutions with one different loads for valid to standards according to counting developed .

Various kind of of foundations technical and economic indicators compare , if they one different reliable if so , it is possible . Otherwise , natural on the foundation of foundations technical and economic indicators in the calculation , build spatial firmness increase according to constructive measures expenses , it to use for addition expenses (from the plan except repair and precipitation monitoring for) , as well as expenses . foundation improvement according to measures account get need .[8]

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